

BEGGARS' PLACES OF BEGGING AND THEIR DAILY INCOME

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Abstract:

As the beggars places of begging and their daily income of the study, an attempt is made to give a succinct integrated of the study the beggars' survey sponsored by the Central Relief Committee, Government of Karnataka. I have done this work under the able guidance of Sri Veerasivashankara Reddy, Retired Chief Planning Officer, Zilla Panchayat, Bellary, and Dr. B. Seshadri, Retired Professor of Economics, Department of Development Studies, Kannada University, Hampi.

The study was undertaken in three selected places in Hospetaluk of Bellary district, namely, Hospet city, Kamalapura town panchayat and Hampi Grama Panchayat. All those beggars who were available on the days of survey in all the three places were considered for a detailed study. The total number of beggars covered by the survey is 296 and out of this, 237 in Hospet, 37 in Hampi, and 22 in Kamalapur.

Beggars covered in the survey give us the impression that religion, caste, gender, age were not a bar for this practice. We found that beggars belonging to various castes, religion, age, gender, language, etc. I had captured the diverse dimensions of beggars in tables.

Beggars are found in places such as places of worship/religious places, bus stations, railway stations, bars and restaurants. Beggars moving from house to house are also found in our sample. Their daily incomes in terms of money are not one and the same for all the beggars; the daily income of beggars is found to vary from place to place, and also from beggar to beggar in the same place.

Beggars' Preferred Places of Begging:

As to the places of begging, beggars' preferences differ. The related data are presented in Table 1

Table 1: Particulars of Preferred Places of Begging

S.No	Particulars	Beggars: Places Preferred								Total
		Places of worship	Bus Station	Railway Station	Bus Station and places of worship	House to house begging	Bus station, worship place and house to house	Bar and Restaurant	Not Responded	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
01	Scheduled Caste	28 (9.5)	15 (5.1)	5 (1.7)	18 (6.1)	7 (2.4)	33 (11.1)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	106 (35.8)
02	Scheduled Tribe	18 (6.1)	8 (2.7)	1 (0.3)	9 (3.0)	4 (1.4)	18 (6.1)	1 (0.3)	0 (0.0)	59 (19.9)
03	OBC	28 (9.5)	17 (5.7)	1 (0.3)	21 (7.1)	5 (1.7)	33 (11.10)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	105 (35.5)
04	General	6 (2.0)	2 (0.7)	0 (0.0)	7 (2.4)	1 (0.3)	7 (2.4)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	23 (7.8)
05	*Others	1 (0.3)	1 (0.3)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (0.3)	3 (1.0)
06	Total	81 (27.4)	43 (14.5)	7 (2.4)	55 (18.6)	17 (5.7)	91 (30.7)	1 (0.3)	1 (0.3)	296 (100.0)

Note: Others refer to the beggars who are dumb

The figures put in brackets are percentages of the related absolute numbers

The data in table, inter alia, show that:

Beggars' preference is highly pronounced in favour of "Places of Worship" and the least preferred place is "bar and restaurants". Of the 296 beggars, 81(27.4%) have expressed their preference in favour of the former, and only one (0.3%) in favour of the latter.

- ✓ But a significant number of beggars have expressed their preference to beg in three places, namely, "bus stands" "places of worship" and from house to house. Such beggars constitute 30.7% (91).
- ✓ Another preferred placetaken individually is "bus stand". Of the 296, 43 (14.5%) beggars have expressed their preference in favour of 'bus stand'.
- ✓ Individually, 'railway station' is not a much preferred place; only 7 beggars (2.4%) have expressed their preference. But the preference in favour of "bus stand" and "places of worship" is sufficiently high-55 out of 296 (18.6%).
- ✓ Across the caste-categories, in all the places considered, SCs and STs together excel all other categories. The position is occupied by OBCs. General category beggars are found in all places, but their preference is more in favour of bus stands, and places of worship.

Table 2: Particulars of Begging Period

S.No	Particulars	Period of Beggary									Total
		Within one year	1-2 Years	3-5 Years	6-10 Years	11-20 Years	21-30 Years	30Years and above	By birth	Not Responded	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
01	Scheduled Caste	17 (5.7)	12 (4.1)	22 (7.4)	22 (7.4)	8 (2.7)	3 (1.0)	5 (1.7)	13 (4.4)	4 (1.4)	106 (35.8)
02	Scheduled Tribe	5 (1.7)	4 (1.4)	10 (3.4)	10 (3.4)	13 (4.4)	8 (2.7)	4 (1.4)	3 (1.0)	2 (0.7)	59 (19.9)
03	OBC	10 (3.4)	16 (5.4)	30 (10.1)	14 (4.7)	18 (6.1)	4 (1.4)	4 (1.4)	7 (2.4)	2 (0.7)	105 (35.5)
04	General	3 (1.0)	2 (0.7)	5 (1.7)	3 (1.0)	7 (2.4)	2 (0.7)	0 (0.0)	1 (0.3)	0 (0.0)	23 (7.8)
05	*Others	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (1.0)	3 (1.0)
06	Total	35 (11.8)	34 (11.5)	67 (22.6)	49 (16.6)	46 (15.5)	17 (5.7)	13 (4.4)	24 (8.1)	11 (3.7)	296 (100.0)

Note: Others refer to the beggars who are dumb

The figures put in brackets are percentages of the related absolute numbers

By examining the data presented in Table 2, researcher may draw the following inferences:

- ✓ The beggars, who have been into begging between 3 and 5 years constitute the highest proportion. They constitute 22.6% (67) of the selected beggars (from those who have responded to our questions—11 have not answered)
- ✓ The next in order come those beggars who have been into begging between 6 and 10 years. They constitute 16.6% (49). And the third position goes to those who come under the time interval of 11-20 years (15.5%).
- ✓ The fourth and fifth positions go respectively to beggars who come under the time intervals of up to one year (11.8%) and 1 to 2 years (11.5%).
- ✓ Those who have been into begging since their birth (8.1%) occupy the sixth position, and the seventh and eighth positions go respectively to those who come under the class intervals of 21-30 years and above 30 years.

The Status (Occupation) of Beggars before Entering into Beggary:

An attempt made identify the occupational status of the selected beggars, before becoming full-time beggars. Of the 296 respondents, 11 did not respond. The related details are presented in Table 3

Table 3: Particulars of the Occupational Status of Beggars before becoming Full-time Beggars

S.No	Particulars	Occupational status before taking up beggary										Total
		Beggary	Agri. and Agricultural labour	Student	House wife	Domestic work	Driver	Coolly	Hamali	Since Jogathi	Not Responded	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	13	14
01	Scheduled Caste	51 (17.2)	24 (8.1)	0 (0.0)	4 (1.4)	3 (1.0)	0 (0.0)	17 (5.7)	0 (0.0)	4 (1.4)	3 (1.0)	106 (35.8)
02	Scheduled Tribe	30 (10.1)	10 (3.4)	1 (0.3)	2 (0.7)	2 (0.7)	1 (0.3)	12 (4.1)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (0.3)	59 (19.9)
03	OBC	40 (13.5)	25 (8.4)	0 (0.0)	5 (1.7)	1 (0.3)	2 (0.7)	27 (9.1)	0 (0.0)	1 (0.3)	4 (1.4)	105 (35.5)
04	General	14 (4.7)	4 (1.4)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (0.3)	3 (1.0)	1 (0.3)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	23 (7.8)
05	*Others	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (1.0)	3 (1.0)
06	Total	135 (45.6)	63 (21.3)	1 (0.3)	11 (3.7)	6 (2.0)	4 (1.4)	59 (19.9)	1 (0.3)	5 (1.7)	11 (3.7)	296 (100.0)

Note: Others refer to the beggars who are dumb

The figures put in brackets are percentages of the related absolute numbers

From the data presented in Table-3, we may draw the following inferences:

- ✓ A large number of respondent- beggars (135) were engaged in some sort of sporadic begging, before taking up begging as a fulltime occupation.
- ✓ Of the remaining 161 beggars covered in the present study did not answer the questions asked.
- ✓ Next to sporadic beggars, in terms of number, the second and third positions go respectively to agriculture and agriculture workers (63) and general labourers (59).
- ✓ Students and hamalies (loading labourers) constitute only one each. Domestic servants and jogathis (5) come next in order.
- ✓ Four drivers had to take up begging on full time basis because they had become disabled due to accidents

- ✓ Caste category-wise, SCs and STs together account for highest numbers who were engaged in sporadic begging and agriculture workers. OBCs occupy the next position. A similar situation is found in respect of beggars who were general labourers before becoming full time beggars.

Caste-Category-Wise Classification of Beggars Regarding Their Desire to Give-Up Begging:

While carrying out the survey, an attempt was also made to ascertain their opinion as to whether they would give up begging if they get alternative earning activities. Some have said ‘yes’, and some have said ‘no’. The related details are given in Table 4.

Table 4: Opinion about Giving- up Beggary

S.No	Particulars	Giving-up Beggary: Beggars' Opinion			Total
		Not willing	Willing	Not Responded	
1	2	3	4	5	6
01	Scheduled Caste	57 (19.3)	41 (13.9)	8 (2.7)	106 (35.8)
02	Scheduled Tribe	42 (14.2)	15 (5.1)	2 (0.7)	59 (19.9)
03	OBC	56 (18.9)	46 (15.5)	3 (1.0)	105 (35.5)
04	General	15 (5.1)	8 (2.7)	0 (0.0)	23 (7.8)
05	*Others	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (1.0)	3 (1.0)
06	Total	170 (57.4)	110 (37.2)	16 (5.4)	296 (100.0)

Note: Others refer to the beggars who are dumb

The figures put in brackets are percentages of the related absolute numbers

From the data presented in Table 4, I come to know that:

- ✓ Of the 296 respondent-beggars, 16 have not answered the question asked. And of the 280 beggars, 110 have expressed their willingness to give-up begging if they get alternative opportunities to earn their livelihood, and 170 have expressed their desire to continue in beggary.
- ✓ In the case of SCs, those who desire to give-up beggary (41) are less than those who intend to continue in beggary (57 the highest among caste-categories). It is also the case with STs.
- ✓ In the case of OBCs, though a similar situation prevails, the number of those who desire to give-up begging is relatively high.

Attitude of Beggars to Undergo Vocational Training:

Keeping their rehabilitation in view, we tried to ascertain their opinion, as to whether they intend to undergo vocational training and then take-up some earning activity. For this question, of the 296 beggars, 17 have not given any answer. The related details are given in Table 5

Table 5: Opinions about Vocational Training

S.No	Particulars	Vocational Training: Beggars' opinion			Total
		Willing Undergo Training	Training Not Wanted	Not Responded	
1	2	3	4	5	6
01	Scheduled Caste	38 (12.8)	59 (19.9)	9 (3.0)	106 (35.8)
02	Scheduled Tribe	14 (4.7)	43 (14.5)	2 (0.7)	59 (19.9)
03	OBC	43 (14.5)	59 (19.9)	3 (1.0)	105 (35.5)
04	General	7 (2.4)	16 (5.4)	0 (0.0)	23 (7.8)
05	*Others	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (1.0)	3 (1.0)
06	Total	102 (34.5)	177 (59.8)	17 (5.7)	296 (100.0)

Note: Others refer to the beggars who are dumb

The figures put in brackets are percentages of the related absolute numbers

The following facts emerge out of the data presented in table-5:

- ✓ Those who expressed their unwillingness to undergo vocational training and then take-up some job are more in number (177) than those who have expressed their willingness to undergo vocational training (102). This indicates that those who want to come out of beggary are less in number than those who want to continue in beggary.
- ✓ Caste category-wise, without any exception, those who do not want to undergo vocational training are more in number than those who want to undergo training.
- ✓ These findings are indicative of the desire of a large number of beggars not to give-up begging.

Classification of Beggars by the Nature of Work they Prefer:

This is slightly a different type of exercise when compared to the one undertaken in section 5; in a way, it is a sequel to the proceeding section. Here, the focus is on the nature of work they prefer if they give-up beggary. The related particulars are given in Table-6.

Table 6: Particulars about the job-preferences of Respondent-Beggars

S.No	Particulars	Any job is acceptable	Inability to work	Work not wanted	Security guard	Vegetable Vending	Business	Willing to go to School	Not Responded	Total
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
01	Scheduled Caste	22 (7.4)	9 (3.0)	51 (17.2)	4 (1.4)	7 (2.4)	8 (2.7)	2 (0.7)	3 (1.0)	106 (35.8)
02	Scheduled Tribe	7 (2.4)	5 (1.7)	35 (11.8)	4 (1.4)	3 (1.0)	2 (0.7)	0 (0.0)	3 (1.0)	59 (19.9)
03	OBC	20 (6.8)	7 (2.4)	50 (16.90)	11 (3.7)	8 (2.7)	7 (2.4)	0 (0.0)	2 (0.7)	105 (35.5)
04	General	2 (0.7)	1 (0.3)	12 (4.1)	3 (1.0)	2 (0.7)	3 (1.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	23 (7.8)
05	*Others	0 (0.0)	1 (0.3)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (0.7)	3 (1.0)
06	Total	51 (17.2)	23 (7.8)	148 (50.0)	22 (7.4)	20 (6.8)	20 (6.8)	2 (0.7)	10 (3.4)	296 (100.0)

Note: Others refer to the beggars who are dumb

The figures put in brackets are percentages of the related absolute numbers

We may draw the following inferences from the data presented in Table 6

- ✓ Of the 296 beggars interviewed, 148(50%) beggars have expressed their unwillingness to take-up any work, and 10(3.4%) have not answered the related question. And 23 (7.8%) have expressed their inability /disability to work.
- ✓ It is interesting to note that 51(17.2%) respondents have expressed their desire to take up any kind of work they get.
- ✓ Of the remaining respondents, 22(7.4%) have expressed their desire to take-up security guards' work, 20(6.8%) vegetable vending, 20(6.8%) general business, and 2(0.7%) have expressed their desire to go to school.
- ✓ These findings would be of help to the Central Relief Committee to plan its rehabilitation programmes.

Classification of Beggars by the Government Facilities Availed:

As far as beggars the most deprived people are concerned, one would expect that being poor, the beggars must have availed the benefits available for the BPL families in Karnataka. An attempt is made in this section to identify the nature and extent of benefits availed by the respondent-beggars. The related details are presented in Table-7, and in the bar-chart that follows the table.

Table 7: Particulars of Government Benefits availed/not availed by the Respondent-Beggary

S.No	Particulars	Government Facilities							Not Responded	Total
		Ration card	Old age Pension	House	Ration card and House	Ration card and Old age Pension	Ration card, Old Age Pension And House	Not availed any facility		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
01	Scheduled Caste	18 (6.1)	0 (0.0)	3 (1.0)	8 (2.7)	2 (0.7)	0 (0.0)	73 (24.7)	2 (0.7)	106 (35.8)
02	Scheduled Tribe	10 (3.4)	0 (0.0)	2 (0.7)	6 (2.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (0.3)	39 (13.2)	1 (0.3)	59 (19.9)
03	OBC	16 (5.4)	4 (1.4)	2 (0.7)	7 (2.4)	1 (0.3)	1 (0.3)	74 (25.0)	0 (0.0)	105 (35.5)
04	General	2 (0.7)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (1.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	18 (6.1)	0 (0.0)	23 (7.8)
05	*Others	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (1.0)	3 (1.0)
06	Total	46 (15.5)	4 (1.4)	7 (2.4)	24 (8.1)	3 (1.0)	2 (0.7)	204 (68.9)	6 (2.0)	296 (100.0)

Note: Others refer to the beggars who are dumb

The figures put in brackets are percentages of the related absolute numbers

From the data presented in Tble-6, we may draw the following inferences:-

- ✓ It is highly distressing to note that the government benefits available to the poor and the marginalised sections of the society are not extended to 204(68.9%) out of 296 respondent beggars. And 10 respondents have not given any response.
- ✓ Among others, 46(15.5%) respondent-beggars have availed Ration Card facility, four (1.4%) have availed Old age Pension, and seven (2.4%), housing facility, and there are some who have availed a combination of two or more facilities.

- ✓ Twenty four beggars(8.1%) have availed both Ration Card and Housing facilities, three(1%) respondents have availed both Ration Card and Old-age Pension, and only two(0.7%) of them have availed three facilities, namely, Ration card, Old-age Pension, and Housing.
- ✓ These findings would be of help to the Central Relief Committee in formulating rehabilitation policies and programmes.

What do Beggars Need to lead a Normal Lifelike Others?

Keeping in view the rehabilitation of the respondent-beggars, an attempt is made to ascertain what kind of help and assistance they need to lead a normal life. The related particulars are presented in Table 8.

Table 8: Particulars of the kind of Assistance and Help the Respondent-Beggars Need

S.No	Particulars	Caste Category					Total
		SC	ST	OBC	General	Not Responded	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
01	Do not want anything	34 (11.5)	21 (7.1)	31 (10.5)	9 (3.0)	0 (0.0)	95 (32.1)
02	Any job	12 (4.1)	3 (1.0)	13 (4.4)	3 (1.0)	0 (0.0)	31 (10.5)
03	Job and Food	1 (0.3)	0 (0.0)	1 (0.3)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (0.7)
04	Food	0 (0.0)	2 (0.7)	1 (0.3)	1 (0.3)	0 (0.0)	4 (1.4)
05	Food and Clothing	2 (0.7)	0 (0.0)	2 (0.7)	1 (0.3)	0 (0.0)	5 (1.7)
06	Food and House	6 (2.0)	5 (1.7)	4 (1.4)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	15 (5.1)
07	Government job	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (0.7)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (0.7)
08	Ration Card, Job and House	8 (2.7)	7 (2.4)	16 (5.4)	4 (1.4)	0 (0.0)	35 (11.8)
09	House	12 (4.1)	10 (3.4)	11 (3.7)	2 (0.7)	0 (0.0)	35 (11.8)
10	House and care taker	1 (0.3)	1 (0.3)	1 (0.3)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (1.0)
11	Money	4 (1.4)	2 (0.7)	6 (2.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	12 (4.1)
12	Bank Loan	2 (0.7)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (0.7)
13	Old age pension and house	13 (4.4)	6 (2.0)	10 (3.4)	2 (0.7)	0 (0.0)	31 (10.5)
14	Land	2 (0.7)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (0.7)
15	School	3 (1.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (0.7)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	5 (1.7)
16	Not Respond	4 (1.4)	2 (0.7)	1 (0.3)	1 (0.3)	3 (1.0)	11 (3.7)
17	Ration card and Old age pension	1 (0.3)	0 (0.0)	2 (0.7)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (1.0)
18	Land and house	1 (0.3)	0 (0.0)	2 (0.7)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (1.0)
19	Total	106 (35.8)	59 (19.9)	105 (35.5)	23 (7.8)	3 (1.0)	296 (100.0)

Note: Others refer to the beggars who are dumb

The figures put in brackets are percentages of the related absolute numbers

From the data presented in Table 7, we may draw the following inferences:

- ✓ Indeed it is surprising to note that 95(32.1%) of the total respondents (296) say that they do not want any kind of benefit from the government. And 11(3.7%) respondents have not answered this question.
- ✓ These who do not want any help are found in all the caste-categories, but their number is more pronounced in SCs(34–11.5%), STs(21– 7.1%), and OBCs(31 – 10.5%).
- ✓ Those who need some kind of work account for 31 members (10.5%). Such respondents figure more in OBCs (13 – 4.4%) and SCs (12 – 4.1%)
- ✓ Those who want three facilities– Ration card, work and house–account for 35 (11.8%). And those who want houses only account for 35 (11.8%).
- ✓ Those who want old-age pension and houses account for 31 (10.5%). Those who need food and houses are 15 (5.1%).
- ✓ Those who want monetary help are 12 (4.1%) respondents.
- ✓ In all other cases, the number is not so significant. But all those who need some kind of help from the government are more in SCs, STs and OBCs, though they are there in all the caste-categories.

Occupation of Beggars' Parents:

With a view to finding out to what extent the occupation of baggers' parents has bearing on the respondents' beggary; a question was asked about their parents' occupation. Of the 296 respondents, two have not responded. The related details are given in Table 9.

Table 9: Particulars of the Occupation of Respondent-Beggars' Parents

S.No	Particulars	Particulars of Occupation			Total
		Beggars	Not Beggars	Not Responded	
1	2	3	4	5	6
01	Scheduled Caste	15 (5.1)	91 (30.7)	0 (0.0)	106 (35.8)
02	Scheduled Tribe	1 (0.3)	58 (19.6)	0 (0.0)	59 (19.9)
03	OBC	11 (3.7)	94 (31.8)	0 (0.0)	105 (35.5)
04	General	3 (1.0)	20 (6.8)	0 (0.0)	23 (7.8)
05	*Others	0 (0.0)	1 (0.3)	2 (0.7)	3 (1.0)
06	Total	30 (10.1)	264 (89.2)	2 (0.7)	296 (100.0)

Note: Others refer to the beggars who are dumb

The figures put in brackets are percentages of the related absolute numbers. The facts that emerge out of the data presented in Table-8 are given below:

- ✓ Of the 296 beggars, the parents of 294 (89.2%) are not beggars; they have not inherited beggary from their parents. And 30 (10.1%) respondents have claimed to be the offspring of beggar-parents.
- ✓ Caste-category-wise, of the beggars belonging to OBCs (105), 94 have not inherited beggary from their parents. It is also the case with SCs (91, out of 106) STs (58 out of 59) and general (20 out of 23).
- ✓ These findings indicate that majority of the respondent- beggars have not inherited beggary from their parents.

Occupation of Beggars' Brothers:

While designing the questionnaire, we also thought of finding out whether anybody else (other than parents) in their families are engaged in beggary particularly their brothers. As such we asked a question about this and their answers are processed, tabulated and presented in Table 10.

Table 10: Particulars of Beggary among the Brothers of Respondent-Beggars

S.No	Particulars	Particulars of Occupation			Total
		Beggars	Not Beggars	Not Responded	
1	2	3	4	5	6
01	Scheduled Caste	16 (5.4)	90 (30.4)	0 (0.0)	106 (35.8)
02	Scheduled Tribe	1 (0.3)	58 (19.6)	0 (0.0)	59 (19.9)
03	OBC	10 (3.4)	95 (32.1)	0 (0.0)	105 (35.5)
04	General	3 (1.0)	20 (6.8)	0 (0.0)	23 (7.8)
05	*Others	0 (0.0)	1 (0.3)	2 (0.7)	3 (1.0)
06	Total	30 (10.1)	264 (89.2)	2 (0.7)	296 (100.0)

Note: Others refer to the beggars who are dumb

The figures put in brackets are percentages of the related absolute numbers

The data presented in Table 9, reveal the following facts. Here it is pertinent to say that the answers of the respondents are the same as those they have given about their parents, presented in Table 9.

- ✓ Of the 296 beggars covered in the present study, two have not responded. And of the 296, beggars, 264 (89.2%) have answered in the negative, that is, their brothers are not engaged in beggary. Thirty (10.1%) of them have answered in the positive, that is, their brothers are engaged in beggary.
- ✓ The overall picture i.e., those who have answered in the negative are more in number (264) good than those who have answered in the positive (30), also holds when we view the data across caste-categories.

Daily Income of Respondent-Beggars:

The daily income of beggars is not one and the same for all the beggars; it differs from person to person. An attempt is made in this section to capture the variations in the earnings of the respondent beggars. Of the 296 beggars, 14 (4.7%) have not responded. The related details are given in Table 11 and in the bar diagram that follows it.

Table 11: Particulars of the Daily Income of Respondent-Beggars

S.No	Particulars	Daily Income									Total
		Rs. 30-40	Rs. 41-50	Rs. 51-100	Rs. 101-200	Not Respon ded	Rs. 201-300	Rs. 301-400	Food grains up to 2kg	Food grains above 2kg	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
01	Scheduled Caste	31 (10.5)	26 (8.8)	34 (11.5)	9 (3.0)	2 (0.7)	3 (1.0)	1 (0.3)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	106 (35.8)
02	Scheduled Tribe	19 (6.4)	11 (3.7)	12 (4.1)	7 (2.4)	4 (1.4)	3 (1.0)	3 (1.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	59 (19.9)
03	OBC	24 (8.1)	12 (4.1)	49 (16.6)	9 (3.0)	4 (1.4)	4 (1.4)	0 (0.0)	2 (0.7)	1 (0.3)	105 (35.5)
04	General	5 (1.7)	3 (1.0)	9 (3.0)	5 (1.7)	1 (0.3)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	23 (7.8)
05	*Others	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (1.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (1.0)
06	Total	79 (26.7)	52 (17.6)	104 (35.1)	30 (10.1)	14 (4.7)	10 (3.4)	4 (1.4)	2 (0.7)	1 (0.3)	296 (100.0)

Note: Others refer to the beggars who are dumb

The figures put in brackets are percentages of the related absolute numbers

The following inferences may be drawn from the data presented in Table-10:

- ✓ The daily income of the majority of the beggars covered in the study lies between Rs. 51/- and Rs. 100/-. This is the case with 104 (35.1%) beggars. Of this 104, 49 belong to OBCs, 34 to SCs, 12 to STs, and 9 to general category.
- ✓ Next in the order comes the daily income range of Rs.30-40. There are 79 members in this income range. In this case 24 members belong to OBCs, 31 to SCs 19 to STs and 5 to general category.
- ✓ Another range of daily income which merits attention is Rs.41-50. In it there are 52 members. Of the 52 members, SCs claim 26, STs 11, OBCs 12, and general category 3.
- ✓ Apart from the above, 30 respondents figure in the daily income range of Rs.101-200, 10 members in the range of Rs.201-300, and only four members in the range of Rs.301-400. In all, it is to be pointed out that the strength of beggars whose daily income ranges from a low of Rs.30/- to high of Rs.100/- is far greater (235) than those whose daily income ranges from a low of Rs.101 to a high of Rs.400/-.

Principal Findings:

- ✓ There appears to be no caste bar for carrying on begging in two places, taken separately, namely, “places of worship” and “bus stations”; beggars belonging to all castes are found begging in these places.
- ✓ There are some persons, who have become beggars as a matter of inheritance. Beggary seems to have attracted more persons in the last two years. Of course, those who have been in the field from three to 20 years are also in large numbers.
- ✓ As far as their livelihood earning activities before becoming beggars, many of them (135 out of 296) were beggars– theirs is case of inheriting beggary. Quite a significant number of them were in agriculture sector– as farmers and agricultural laborers (63) –and general labourers (59).
- ✓ As to the causes for landing into beggary, for majority of them (247) it is a matter of unilateral interest.
- ✓ Of them, those who do not want to give up beggary (170) even if an alternative livelihood opportunity is available, and others (110) expressed their desire to give-up beggary and to take-up alternative earning activity.
- ✓ Those who have expressed their willingness to undergo vocational training are less in number than those who have expressed their willingness to undergo vocational training.
- ✓ As to the nature of work they would like to take-up, if provided, 50% of them have said that they do not want any work at all. And 17.2% of them have expressed their desire to take-up any kind of work.
- ✓ Some of the respondent-beggars (15.5%) have been availing the benefit of ration card.
- ✓ The parents and brothers of most beggars are not beggars.

The daily income of most beggar (104) lies in the range of Rs.51-100. And next in the order are those whose daily income is between Rs.30 and 40

References:

1. Neetha Lal “Kriminalising beggars ested of rehabilitating them” Dehli, efo change news and futures, June 2007
2. Fahadhameedrana “begging a sickening nuisance” website www.straightdope.com/mailbag/mbegprofit.html.
3. Shrivathsava k and Santosh “A public audit of beggary relief system” Rarstothansankalp, Bangalore, 2010

4. The Karnataka prohibition of beggary act-1975 and (amendment act-1982, 1988, 2002)", Central Relief Committee, Govt.of Karnataka. Bangalore.
5. "Rules for the prohibition of beggary act-1975 and (amendment act-1990&1997)" Central Relief Committee, Government of Karnataka, Bangalore
6. Krishna B.R., "Aparadhashashtra", Vidyanihiprakashana, Gadag, 1995.